

Evolution of the conceptual design of a full-scale compliant camber morphing flap for the next generation Hybrid Electrical Aircraft

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To enhance high-lift performance and reduce fuel consumption per flight, wing structures may be equipped with compliant morphing devices, which can exhibit precise and smooth adjustment of their subcomponents' shapes in response to varying operational conditions. Such a capability is due to their structural stiffness distribution, typically derived from an optimization design process, specifically engineered to enable significant deformations, while maintaining sufficient robustness and preserving a defined shape under external aerodynamic forces. In the European project HERWINGT (Hybrid Electric Regional Wing Integration Novel Green Technologies), backed and funded by the Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking (JU), CIRA has developed a compliant morphing flap (MF) concept for a strut-braced wing application on the next-generation Hybrid Electric Regional Aircraft (HERA). The focus of this work is on the progression of the MF conceptual architectures developed throughout the mentioned project, examining various preliminary designs and considering factors related to the integration of the actuation system. A systematic design approach, incorporating trade-off finite element analyses, is here described for three MF configurations, with a critical evaluation of the technical results and lessons learned from each development. Finally, justifications for the down-selection of the engineering solution suitable for the future advanced design of the MF are presented.

I. Nomenclature

<i>A/C</i>	= Aircraft
C_p	= Pressure Coefficient
<i>c</i>	= Chord
<i>CI/C2/C3</i>	= 1 st /2 nd /3 rd Morphing Flap Design Configuration
<i>CIRA</i>	= Italian Aerospace Research Centre
<i>DEMO</i>	= Demonstrator
<i>FEA/M</i>	= Finite Element Analysis/Model
<i>HEPS</i>	= Hybrid-Electric Propulsion Systems
<i>HERA</i>	= Hybrid-Electric Regional Aircraft
<i>MF</i>	= Morphing Flap
<i>SAF</i>	= Sustainable Aviation Fuels
<i>SoA</i>	= State of the Art
V_D	= Dive Speed
V_F	= Maximum Extended Flapped Speed

II. Introduction

The aerospace industry is increasingly prioritizing the reduction of carbon emissions and the integration of renewable energy sources. Thus, Hybrid-Electric Propulsion Systems (HEPS) are emerging as a leading solution for achieving

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more efficient, cleaner, and quieter aeronautical propulsion. The comparison between HEPS and traditional propulsion systems reported in [1] highlights the benefits of the former impacting on:

- Reduced emissions and noise
- Enhanced aircraft power distribution and quality
- Improved global aircraft efficiency

Moreover, HEPS is expected to bring about significant changes in terms of design and architectures of next-generation aircraft. Estimates, [2], suggest that these advancements will influence technological development trends in aviation over the next 30 years. To further promote sustainable and climate-neutral aviation, various technologies are being explored. Among all, morphing wing devices are promising, due to the potential of enhancing aerodynamic performance, leading to reduced fuel consumption and noise. In this context, the European Union has funded the HERWINGT (Hybrid-Electric Regional Wing Integration Novel Wing Technologies) project through the Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking (JU). The main aim of such a project is to drive technological advancements toward decarbonizing aviation systems, [3]. Specifically, HERWINGT focuses on developing, validating, and demonstrating key technologies for an innovative high aspect-ratio strut-braced wing design tailored for a 100-seat short-range Hybrid Electric Regional Aircraft (HERA), [4]. The combination of all these novel solutions will lead to a reduction of 50% at aircraft level, compared to the 2020 State-of-the-Art (SoA) A/C. More in detail, the advancements in aircraft design focus on several key areas:

- Enhanced Aerodynamic Wing Configurations: These improvements aim to reduce drag and fuel consumption at the wing component level.
- Innovative Wing Structures: The integration of cutting-edge systems and new material technologies leads to significant weight reductions at the component level.
- Hybrid-Electrical Technology Development: This includes technologies that support the use of hybrid-electric systems, incorporating hydrogen/batteries alongside fuel systems utilizing Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAF).

As part of this initiative, the Italian Aerospace Research Centre (CIRA) is actively engaged in designing and developing a morphing flap concept intended for integration into a high aspect-ratio wing of hybrid-electric regional aircraft. The CIRA involvement focuses on the design of a full-scale morphing flap based on a compliant architecture, which differs from traditional finger-like mechanism-based adaptive structures. Compliant morphing concepts account for controlled deformation of the internal subcomponents, allowing for smooth modifications to the overall shape of the assembly, [5]. The structural stiffness is, thus, carefully optimized to ensure adequate compliance for accommodating large deformations while maintaining sufficient robustness to withstand external aerodynamic loads, [6].

III. Aim of the work and approach

The design objective pursued by the Italian Aerospace Research Centre (CIRA) Adaptive Structures Division concerns a full-scale morphing flap, intended for integration into a specified reference wing.

CIRA's efforts focus on:

- The structural design of a full-size camber morphing flap.
- The advanced design of the camber morphing flap for incorporation into a single-bay (0.5 m) demonstrator, which will undergo static, dynamic, and fatigue testing.

This paper pertains to the conceptual design of the MF DEMO, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 - CIRA activities at HERWINGT project level, with a focus on the aim of this work, [7]

To achieve that, a proper multi-step design approach has been conceived and already described by the authors in [7], here reported just for the sake of clarity.

Beginning with the definition of requirements, an initial 2D aerodynamic evaluation was conducted to derive aerodynamic shapes and loads. This data was simultaneously utilized as input for two different configurations, referred

to as C1 and C2, which were developed and analyzed as structural layouts and actuation systems, also considering the industrial collaboration with Collins regarding actuation aspects.

The meticulous process of concept selection resulted in a new third configuration, C3, incorporating the optimal features from both C1 and C2.

The details of the C3 configuration, which was subsequently employed for the 3D aerodynamic assessment and ultimately contributed to the advanced design of the MF DEMO, are presented within the scope of this work, as an integration of [7].

For all the configurations, compliant architecture was selected to enable wing morphing capabilities. Such a choice was led by the fact that, in general, compliant morphing devices allow for precise deformation of subcomponents to smoothly change the overall shape of the assembly. The structural stiffness is meticulously engineered to ensure adequate compliance for significant deformations while maintaining sufficient robustness to preserve a specific shape under external aerodynamic forces.

IV. Reference wing

Fig. 2 illustrates the reference wing used for the achievement of the goal of this work, also depicting a detailed table of useful geometrical features.

The area chosen for the development of the MF DEMO design is the non-tapered inner flap root section, which has a rectangular shape, and a span extension of 0.5 m.

Fig. 2 – MF DEMO investigation region and geometrical detail of the reference wing and morphing flap, [7]

V. Conceptual design (C1, C2, C3)

The wing load calculation was carried out by the CIRA aerodynamic team, using their proprietary Unsteady Zonal Euler Navier Stokes (RANS) flow solver, which applies compressible RANS equations on structured multi-block domains. As detailed in [8], the aerodynamic evaluation began with the preliminary assumption of a uniform load distribution along the wing's span, due to the rectangular shape of the reference geometry. The two-dimensional profile chosen for this calculation corresponded to the maximum wing load. Going further in detail, the assessment of aerodynamic loads was conducted under two conditions:

- Flapped (high-lift) condition: this corresponds to the maximum extended speed for the flap (V_F) of 90 m/s with a load factor of 2.
- Clean (high-speed) condition: this is associated with the dive speed (V_D) and a load factor of 2.5.

For the MF DEMO conceptual design, the flapped condition was selected, as illustrated in Fig. 3, which shows the 2D aerodynamic pressure distribution (orange curve) alongside the reference airfoil profile in its morphed configuration (blue curve).

Observing the project structural requirement of obtaining the target morphed down shape through an equivalent rigid rotation angle of about 17° , [7], in the following subsection, the three configurations developed within the trade-off design process of the DEMO MF are discussed separately.

Fig. 3 - 2D Preliminary Aerodynamic pressure distribution (orange curve) and reference airfoil profile (blue curve). Morphed down configuration corresponding to the V_F and load factor = 2, [7]

A. C1 – Truss-rib configuration, conceptual design

The first architecture investigated in the trade-off design process object of this study is a truss rib configuration, inspired by the one reported in [9] and shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 - C1 truss-rib based structural layout: upper skin (a), and lower skin and compliant rib (b), [7]

The morphing skin design features a one-piece composite structure, where the upper and lower sections are seamlessly connected at the trailing edge tip. Additionally, the lower section of the skin is capable of sliding in the chordwise direction, under the action of a linear actuation system pulling it along the x direction. More, such one-bay architecture is equipped with two compliant truss ribs (left and right), properly attached to the skin, exhibiting a carefully selected stiffness distribution throughout the truss components.

A dedicated FE model has been developed to perform FEA in Nastran® environment under the high-lift load condition previously described, to map stress and strain distribution, also accounting a trade-off in terms of actuation locking force.

More in detail, the preliminary C1 FEM comprises 9,912 elements and 10,148 nodes. Specifically:

- The truss ribs are represented using 1D-beam elements made of aluminium, featuring a uniform cross-section of 2 cm by 1 cm.
- For the skin, shell element properties have been applied. Two distinct loops of FE analysis were conducted, varying in material and skin thickness, as detailed below:
 - **Loop 0:** Aluminum material with a consistent thickness of 1.5 mm.
 - **Loop 1:** Carbon fiber laminate with a uniform thickness of 2.4 mm.

The connection between the skin and the ribs has been modelled using Multi Point Constraints (MPCs) as rigid elements. A schematic representation of the C1 finite element model is provided in Figure 5.

Fig. 5 – C1 FEM

Under reasonable BCs, as in [7], the main outcomes resulting from preliminary FEA are listed below and shown in Fig. 6.

- The target tip vertical deflection of about 15 cm is achieved; the actual morphed down shape, instead, is not achieved.
- The two ribs appear as the most stressed structural components.
- The actuator locking force are in the order of magnitude of 10^5 N.

Fig. 6 – C1 FEA results: a) displacements distribution (high-lift load condition); b) Von-Mises stress (high-lift load condition); c) actuation locking force trade off (no aero. Loads); d) Von-Mises stress (actuation loads only), [7]

B. C2 – X-rib configuration, conceptual design

The second layout, namely C2, investigated in the MF DEMO trade-off design procedure, accounts for an X-Rib configuration, Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 – C2 X-rib initial structural layout, with two linear actuators

An initial finite element (FE) model, primarily based on 1D beam-like elements, was developed for genetic optimization design, [10]:[13]. This approach aimed to simplify the architecture and decrease the number of actuators, from two to one, [14].

The coarse FE model, created for the purpose of verifying flexibility, was chosen as it effectively balanced the preliminary results to be analyzed—such as displacements and stress distributions—with the required computational effort [15].

All one-dimensional elements were modelled in aluminum, characterized by the following properties:

- $E = 7.00E+10 \text{ N/m}^2$
- Poisson Ratio = 0.320
- $G = 2.65E+10 \text{ N/m}^2$
- $\rho = 2780 \text{ kg/m}^3$

A schematic representation of the C2 and one-actuator based FEM, resulting from the initial genetic optimization is illustrated in Figure 8.

Fig. 8 – C2 FEM, [7]

Preliminary FEA have been performed: as a main result, local stress spikes were found out, probably due to local gradient effects, Fig. 9. Analyses results in terms of linear actuation locking forces are in Fig. 10. The order of magnitude of such force resulted in 10^3 N.

Fig. 9 – C2 FEA results, Von-Mises stress distribution, [7]

Fig. 10 – C2 actuator locking force vs actuator stroke, [7]

C. C3, hybrid configuration, conceptual design

The final configuration, C3 or hybrid conf., was developed by accounting for the best structural features resulting from both the C1 and C2 configurations, considering the preliminary FEA results.

Figure 11 shows a representation of the C3 system layout.

Fig. 11 – C3 system layout

The structural layout includes, in this case, an Aluminum skin (heritage from C2), with the lower portion capable of sliding along the chordwise direction. A no-constant thickness (see color map in fig 11.) was included, deriving from the optimization process. Moreover, a vertical web, properly connected to the upper and the lower skin, was introduced. Two external (heritage from C1) linear actuators, connected to a rod moving the lower skin, have been placed in the wing box. The contraction of the actuators along the chordwise direction allows the sliding motion of the skin.

A finite element model was generated through an in-house genetic MATLAB algorithm, by following the optimization process exploded into Fig. 12.

Fig. 12 – C3 genetic algorithm-based FEM generation process

Constraints concerning reasonable criteria based on buckling, static and dynamic aspects have been introduced to obtain a robust model, [16]:[26]. The static runs showed stabilization after 25 iterations in terms of the fitness function, defined as the inverse of the squared of the maximum deviation between the actual and the target morphed shapes.

Then, all the configurations' outputs of the optimization process here described, have been analyzed in terms of performances and shapes. A normalization of all the design parameters was achieved, to have an instantaneous map of the behavior of each configuration with respect to the identified criteria, leading to the best candidate solution, Fig. 13, optimal compromise from static, dynamic and actuation system point of view.

Fig. 13 – C3 final configuration: clean, target, actuated and actuated with aero. Loads shapes

This final version of the C3 configuration was implemented in a new and optimized FEM, subjected to further FEA, under the action of aerodynamic and/or actuation loads. The main FEA results have been reported in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14 – C3 final FEA results, with and without aero. Loads: max displacements (a) and b)); max Von-Mises stress ((c) and d)); max actuation chordwise force (e) and f))

The main results show that the target tip vertical deflection is almost reached; the actual morphed shape well fits the target one. Moreover, the actuation x Force component is lower with respect to the C1 and C2 cases.

VI. Conclusions

Morphing wing structures are a key technology aimed at enhancing the aerodynamic efficiency of next-generation hybrid-electric regional aircraft. These structures can continuously adjust their shape during flight, responding dynamically to varying aerodynamic conditions. The increasing focus on automated manufacturing, assembly, and integration techniques for aircraft components has opened opportunities to exploit lightweight designs driven by simulation and to fully utilize topology optimization methods. For example, additive manufacturing is an effective approach for creating complex structural components as well as smaller fittings, joints, and ribs, offering significant advantages over traditional metalworking processes.

This study focuses on the conceptual design of a full-scale compliant morphing flap, considering the aerodynamic loads calculated in the project's initial stages. The design efforts are aimed at maximizing the benefits of optimization for the advanced development of the morphing flap device. The results of the trade-off among three different configurations, investigated in terms of performance and accounting actuation system aspects, led to the selection of

the third configuration here discussed to advance this concept towards demonstration. Additional structural enhancements will be necessary to eliminate material redundancy to address the MF advanced design.

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